

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D2.4.1

Survey covering status of long-term preservation and long-term archiving in ESS in Germany

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the findings of an online survey conducted to assess current practices for long-term storage and archiving of digital data in Earth System Sciences (ESS) in Germany. The aim of the survey was to achieve a comprehensive overview about the current setup of long-term preservation of ESS data in Germany. The survey was conducted between 8th March and 23th April 2023. Included in this deliverable are the complete edited results and corresponding charts of the survey (Appendix 1) as well as the raw data of the survey results (Appendix 2), both available in German. The insights gained from this survey will directly inform the development of comprehensive guidelines for long-term ESS data preservation within the NFDI4Earth project.

Abbreviations

ESS - Earth system sciences

LTA - Long-term archiving

LTS - Long-term storage

M2.4 - Measure 2.4 Data in Long-Term Storage

RDM - Research data management

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1. Introduction

In the NFDI4Earth measure M2.4 "Data in Long-Term Storage" our aim is to contribute to an improvement of long-term storage (LTS) and long-term archiving (LTA) of digital data in Earth System Sciences (ESS). The primary output of the measure M2.4 will be the development of consolidated guidelines and recommendations covering various aspects of digital long-term preservation of ESS data, addressing different stakeholders relevant for a successful LTS and LTA of relevant ESS data.

To gain an overview of the current status of the current setup on LTS and LTA in ESS in Germany we conducted an online survey ("Online-Umfrage zur Langzeitspeicherung und Langzeitarchivierung von Daten in den Erdsystemwissenschaften") between 8th March and 23th April 2023 via the LimeSurvey-Service provided to the NFDI4Earth by TU Dresden (via Bildungsportal Sachsen). In order to reach as many different stakeholders as possible, including governmental agencies, the language chosen for conducting the survey was German. An updated version of this survey is planned for 2025, in order to track changes and improvements in the community as well as the potential impact of the work and services developed in the NFDI4Earth on digital long-term preservation of ESS data.

This deliverable presents an evaluation of the survey's key findings. Included in this deliverable are the complete edited results and corresponding charts of the survey (Appendix 1) as well as the raw data (direct export from LimeSurvey) of the survey results (Appendix 2), both available in German.

2. Methodology

The survey was conducted anonymously, in order for the survey participants to be able to answer as openly and frankly as possible. The survey contained altogether 36 questions, including optional follow-up questions conditionally shown only on specific answers of preceding questions (accordingly indicated for every question in Appendix 1). The last two questions contained organisational aspects regarding the NFDI4Earth Interest Group Long-term Storage and Archiving and are not included in Appendix 1. For many of these questions the survey offered participants the opportunity to provide in depth free text answers. The intention was to enquire as detailed information as possible on the current setup of digital long-term preservation in ESS. In the preparation and analysis of the survey results the free text answers were coded and, as far as practicable, related answers grouped into overarching categories. This is indicated for the respective answers by the note "Code" in Appendix 1. Answers that did not correlate with the question were subsumed in the category "weitere Angaben". The number of survey participants who answered each question (indicated accordingly for every question in Appendix 1) was used as the data basis for calculating the percentage for the individual answers. In Appendix 1 the percentages are rounded to two decimal places, whereas in this document they are rounded to whole numbers.

In our survey we distinguished, where applicable, between long-term storage and long-term archiving, which we defined in the introduction to the survey as follows:

- Long-term storage of data (LTS): The duration of long-term storage is usually 10 years
- Long-term archiving of data (LTA): Long-term archiving is designed for an indefinite period of time

For questions regarding data volume, file formats and metadata in use we distinguished furthermore between LTS, LTA as well as "for ongoing work" and "for publication".

The survey was promoted and distributed via different channels, aiming to reach different stakeholders and a broad target audience in the ESS community. This included the use of all relevant NFDI4Earth-channels (mailing lists, news entry on the NFDI4Earth-website and social media), the mobilization of existing networks of the participating institution in M2.4 as well as the request to all NFDI-participants to distribute the survey to their colleagues and via their channels.

A total of 106 participants (not including 23 participants that only visited the starting page of the survey) initially took part in our survey, though this number decreased gradually over the survey to 54 for mandatory questions. For optional follow-up questions the number of responses is even lower. Due to this and the relatively low number of responses altogether, the survey results were not broken down by discipline or role of the survey participants. This evaluation, based solely on the survey results, gives an indication of the current setup on LTS and LTA in ESS in Germany, but is not necessarily, due to the relatively low number of responses, representative for all disciplines within ESS in Germany.

3. Survey results

3.1. Survey participants

In order to get a clearer overview on the outreach of the survey across the diverse ESS-landscape, we asked respondents to provide information on the discipline, the primary role of their work activity as well as the kind of institution they are working in, using single choice questions (see Appendix 1, Q1-3). Looking at the distribution of the respondents by disciplines, by far the most participants allocated themselves to Atmospheric Science, Oceanography and Climate Research (30%) and Geophysics and Geodesy (28%), followed by Geography (10%) and Geology and Palaeontology (9%). Having the choice between two answers in regard to their primary role, the answers here were almost equally split between working primarily scientifically (49%) and working as infrastructure providers (50%). Most survey respondents work in non-university research institutions (48%), followed by governmental agencies (31%) and universities (19%).

3.2. Data volume and file formats in use

In ESS the data volume being accumulated over time can quickly reach a substantial size, posing a challenge of scale from a long-term preservation perspective. In our survey we inquired about the data volume being generated annually (see Appendix 1, Q5), distinguishing between data for ongoing work, LTS, LTA and for publication.

Table 1: data volume being generated annually according to point in time

	don't know	nil	≤ 1 GB	≤ 100 GB	≤ 1 TB	≤ 100 TB	≤ 1 PB	> 1 PB
for ongoing work	20%	1%	11%	11%	20%	29%	2%	6%
for LTS	28%	2%	5%	16%	11%	29%	6%	2%
for LTA	31%	4%	6%	12%	19%	19%	6%	4%
for publication	21%	2%	17%	27%	19%	11%	1%	1%

As seen in table 1 most respondents, disregarding the responses "don't know", are generating data in the range between 1-100TB annually for all categories except "publication".

Since a successful long-term preservation of digital data depends heavily on the usage of stable, sustainable and well documented file formats that can be interpreted by software environments over a long period of time, we asked our survey participants to name up to four most commonly used file formats for their data, distinguishing again between file formats used for ongoing work, LTS, LTA and for publication.

Table 2: commonly used file formats in use according to point in time

	most used file format	second most used file format	third most used file format	fourth most used file format
for ongoing work	csv (48%)	nc/netcdf (44%)	txt (16%)	shp/shapefile (16%)
for LTS	csv (45%)	nc/netcdf (41%)	tiff (20%)	pdf (20%)
for LTA	nc/netcdf (42%)	csv (40%)	pdf (21%)	tiff (17%)

	most used file format	second most used file format	third most used file format	fourth most used file format
for publi- cation	nc/netcdf (46%)	csv (40%)	pdf (22%)	xlsx & tiff (both 12%)

As seen in table 2 according to our survey the most commonly used file formats at any point in time in ESS in Germany are csv and nc/netcdf, both being used by over 40% of the respondents, followed by the file formats pdf and tiff (for complete results see Appendix 1, Q6). From a long-term preservation perspective, the status quo regarding file formats used is encouraging, since the most commonly used file formats largely meet the requirements for sustainable file formats suitable for long-term preservation.

3.3. Metadata in use

Digital long-term preservation requires having sufficient information about data in terms of metadata description and documentation on several levels. In our survey we asked about the point in time metadata about data is created, which categories of metadata is typically collected and whether and which metadata schemas are being used.

According to our survey results the most common point in time for creating metadata (see Appendix 1, Q7) is during ongoing work with data (64%), with steadily decreasing proportions at the points before data publication (58%), before handing over data for LTS (32%) and before handing over data for LTA (26%). Few indicated not creating any metadata at all (9%).

Looking at the categories of metadata being collected (compare table 3 and Appendix 1, Q8), it stands out that metadata for administrative details (e.g. file format, required software, etc.) are least likely being collected in almost every point in time. This poses a challenge especially for LTA, since sufficient information in this category is essential for being able to keep data accessible and interpretable over time especially via migrating data to current file formats.

Table 3: categories of metadata being collected according to point in time

	metadata for description of content	metadata for origin of data	metadata for legal aspects	metadata for administrative details (e.g. file format, required software, etc.)
for ongoing work	71%	48%	20%	30%
for LTS	57%	48%	43%	34%
for LTA	55%	52%	45%	38%
for publication	70%	63%	55%	45%

From the respondents collecting metadata about their data only slightly more than half (56%) are using a metadata schema. The employed metadata schemas are incredibly diverse (see Appendix 1, Q9a), reflecting the diverse landscape and disciplines in ESS, with Dublin Core being mentioned most frequently (up to 20% of the respondents).

3.4. Availability and awareness of support and guidelines on LTS and LTA

Asking the survey participants about known contact points for support on LTS and LTA (see Appendix 1, Q10 and 11), only 66% were aware of any for LTS and exactly 50% for LTA. For LTS the primary known contact point is the respondent's institutions own repository, IT-department, computing centre, library or RDM (34%), followed by Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum (DKRZ)/World Data Center for Climate (WDCC¹) (24%) and PANGAEA² (18%). For LTA the primary known contact point is DKRZ/WDCC (34%), followed by the respondent's institutions own repository, IT-department, computing centre, library or RDM (28%), PANGAEA and state archives (both 14%). These results indicate that there is still a significant proportion of respondents unaware where to turn to as well as the lack of one central well known entity in ESS in Germany for support on questions regarding LTS and LTA of their data.

¹ <https://www.wdc-climate.de>

² <https://pangaea.de/>

Regarding known guidelines that address LTS and LTA (see Appendix 1, Q12), over a third (38%) of the respondents are not aware of any, half (50%) named the DFG Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice, followed by the respondent's own institutional guidelines (29%). Asking about the existence of guidelines for a systematic RDM in the respondent's own institution (see Appendix 1, Q13) only 36% answered yes. Of those only slightly more than half (57%) stated that guidelines on LTS and/or LTA are included therein. This shows that LTS and LTA are quite often not addressed in existing guidelines.

3.5. Existence and implementation of long-term preservation strategies and policies

Securing the long-term interpretability and availability of digital data is an active process of maintaining and curating data over time. Thus, having adequate strategies and policies in place, addressing responsibilities as well as necessary tasks is essential for a successful long-term preservation of digital data.

Asking in a multiple-choice question (see Appendix 1, Q16) whether preservation strategies for maintaining the readability and interpretability of data in the long-term are being at the respondent's institution in place the overwhelming majority answered that they were not aware of any (61%). 13% of the respondents answered that there were no respective strategies in place, bitstream preservation was indicated by 17%, migration strategy by 11% and emulation strategy by 6%. Inquiring about having a long-term archiving or preservation planning policy in place (see Appendix 1, Q 17) only 13% of the respondents answered yes, with the overwhelming majority indicating again that they are not aware of any (69%). A similar picture emerges regarding the existence of defined criteria for archival appraisal for data in the respondent's institution (see Appendix 1, Q18). Only 20% of the respondents indicated having respective criteria in place, 37% not having any and 43% that they were not aware of any.

These results indicate that in many institutions strategies and policies regarding long-term preservation of digital data are not existent and/or staff and scientists are not being aware of them. Especially the low number of respondents indicating having any kind of long-term preservation strategy at their institution in place is a concerning conclusion, illustrating the need for further support in this area.

3.6. Existing workflows for LTS and LTA

Asking about the existence of established workflows for LTS and LTA of data in the respondent's institution (see Appendix 1, Q19 and 20), only 37% of the respondents indicated that they exist for LTS and 19% for LTA. For LTS the established workflows include data transfer to an external repository, archive or computing centre (38%) and data transfer to an internal computing centre and IT-department or archive (25%). 38% of the respondents have department or working group specific workflows for LTS in place. For LTA the established workflows

include data transfer to an external repository, archive or computing centre (63%) and data transfer to an internal computing centre and IT-department or archive (25%).

Inquiring about the existence of automated interfaces for transferring data to a repository or archive (see Appendix 1, Q21), most of the respondents answered that they exist at their institution (37%), 33% answered that they do not, while 30% indicated that they are not aware of any.

3.7. Topics of desired support on LTS and LTA

At the end of the survey, we asked the survey participants in a free text question on which aspects of LTS and LTA they would like to have more support and information in form of specific guidelines or recommendations (see Appendix 1, Q23). The most desired topic was on concepts and (implementation) strategies on LTA (24%), followed by criteria for archival appraisal and retention periods of data (17%) and recommended data formats and data types for LTA (14%). Furthermore 17% of the respondents indicated that they wish to receive more comprehensive information on all aspects of long-term preservation.

4. Conclusion

In summary, the survey results indicate a mixed picture regarding the current status on LTS and LTA in ESS in Germany. Regarding the use of sustainable file formats, suitable for long-term preservation, ESS in Germany appears to be well positioned. The level of documentation and collected metadata about data, as well as the use of metadata schemas, still seems improvable, especially in regard to collecting comprehensively all specifically relevant and required information for LTA.

Long-term preservation strategies, policies and guidelines seem to be at many institutions not in place or the staff and scientists not aware of them, indicating an uncertainty on what data to archive, where to turn to with questions regarding LTS and LTA as well as what workflows and requirements for LTA to follow. These results correlate with the mentioned aspects on LTS and LTA that most respondents wish to receive more support and information in form of specific guidelines or recommendations. This and the relatively high number of respondents wishing for more comprehensive information on all aspects of long-term preservation also illustrates the need for further educational resources.

The NFDI4Earth's aim is therefore to raise awareness in the ESS community on challenges and requirements as well as develop solutions, strategies and guidelines for digital long-term preservation of ESS data, offering the ESS community a central entry point on information and guidance of digital long-term preservation. Within the measure M2.4, among other things, guidelines on specific aspects of long-term preservation will be developed, such as "Guidelines

for the preparation of data for archiving", "Guidelines for repository providers" and "Guidelines for the appraisal of ESS data for long-term preservation and archiving". In these guidelines the survey results will also be taken into account and incorporated.

The experiences gained from this survey will inform the refinement and execution of an updated version of the survey scheduled for 2025. Particularly the wide use of free text answers has to be reconsidered, since it seemed to have discouraged some respondents to finish the survey. Furthermore, the approach for promotion and distribution of the survey scheduled for 2025 will be re-evaluated, in order to achieve a higher number of respondents.